

Development and Deployment of Autonomous Scale Submarine Models for Hydrodynamic Testing of U.S. Navy Submarine Maneuvering Characteristics

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Abstract— Understanding the hydrodynamic maneuvering capabilities of our Navy’s submarines is a vital aspect of submarine design and in-service life. In the Hydrodynamics Testing Branch at the Naval Surface Warfare Center, Carderock Division (NSWCCD), autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) that are scale models of the Navy’s submarines are developed to provide high fidelity data on maneuvering characteristics. These vehicles not only function as AUVs with a standard suite of navigation functionality, but they also perform a vehicle maneuver to replicate the full scale submarine’s capability and collect hundreds of channels of data that are used for analysis and simulation validation. The Autonomous Submarine Models are tested in unique indoor and outdoor facilities that provide extensive technological and personnel support for vehicle maneuvering testing and analysis. This paper describes the technology and innovations that are used in the hydrodynamic testing of autonomous scale models of our Navy’s submarines including control, navigation, data collection, and test deployment.

Keywords—submarine; model; autonomous; vehicle; Navy

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Submarine Maneuvering Characterization

The characterization process for maneuvering and control of the U.S. Navy submarines performed by the Naval Surface Warfare Center, Carderock Division (NSWCCD) has many facets as shown in Fig. 1. Central to this process is the simulation and analysis tool, which is a geometry-physics based modeling tool capable of predicting 6 degree-of-freedom (DOF) trajectories of a submerged vehicle over an expected range of operating and environmental conditions. This tool accepts a range of geometry and experimental inputs which fine tune the accuracy of the deliverables of the process. These deliverables include contributions to the submerged operating envelope of the Navy’s submarines, fleet guidance, ship systems manuals, automatic control algorithms, ship control trainers, and hydrodynamic load calculations.

Scale model testing plays a critical role in the characterization process. The scale model tests include the entire hydrodynamic system of the submarine and are performed at a high enough Reynolds number that the results can be

adequately scaled to represent full-scale performance. Scale model experiments consist of two types, captive and free-running. Captive models are towed through the water and data is collected over a tether while free-running models are self-propelled, self-maneuvered and data is stored on-board or sent across a wireless data link. Captive model testing provides the capability of isolating hydrodynamic parameters by towing the model through the water at varying speeds, model orientations, and propeller rpm. In free-running model testing, model data is measured during realistic submarine maneuvers that include combined motions not able to be replicated with a captive model. The data collected with free-running models has become essential to the submarine maneuvering characterization process and has resulted in the development of a sophisticated system that combines robotics and autonomous underwater vehicle technology with a high fidelity data acquisition system. The information regarding the submarine maneuvering characterization process was obtained from a limited distribution U.S. Navy Report.

B. History of Free-running Model Testing

Since its inception in 1898, NSWCCD has been using scale models for design and performance evaluation of the United States Navy’s ships and submarines. Throughout NSWCCD’s history, submarine models have been traditionally captive. However, it was recognized in the 1970’s that in order to fully determine the performance characteristics of the submarines, including combined motions, free-running model testing would need to be performed. A radio-controlled model (RCM) using pulse-code modulated FM transmission was developed and operated for over 20 years, providing free-running maneuvering data for the development of submerged operating envelopes (SOE) for the U.S. Navy submarine fleet. However, the maneuvers that the RCM was capable of performing were limited by the depth penetration range of the FM transmissions. Furthermore the RCM was restricted to running in a 20 ft deep indoor test basin, limiting maneuvering ranges to within the basin’s 360 ft by 240 ft area. This led to reliance on mathematical predictions for maneuvering characteristics outside the RCMs capability. Since these predictions were not experimentally verified, large error bands were used to provide a conservative operating guidance.

Fig. 1. Maneuvering Characterization Process

Beginning in 2004, motivated by the limitations of the RCM, an autonomous model (AM) was developed using the mechanical structure of the RCM as a platform [1]. This system uses two PC-104 single board computers with software written in C and FORTRAN to control the model through maneuvers and collect data at 100 Hz. The AM is also equipped with a sophisticated ballast system, navigation sensors, and a fault recovery system. This system extended the capability of the free-running model testing considerably, adding range and depth to the maneuvers and allowing the model to be deployed in outdoor test ranges. These improvements over the RCM platform allowed for validation of mathematical predictions over a larger functional domain resulting in more accurate operating guidance for the submarines.

Recently, the AM has undergone another overhaul to increase capability and add functionality. The internal control system has been upgraded to run on desktop level processing computers and the data acquisition system has been replaced with high frequency, high resolution capable hardware. The navigation system has been upgraded with RTK GPS, an inertial navigation unit (INU), and an acoustic tracking system. Additionally, the fault recovery system has been replaced with a

single-board computer with a FPGA that provides a more flexible and adaptable fail safe system. Lead-acid batteries have been replaced with a lithium phosphate system that significantly increases run time between charging. The following sections detail the architecture of this new AM system and highlight its capabilities and testing procedures.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

A. Overview

The Hydrodynamics Testing Branch at NSWCCD operates the autonomous submarine models to provide maneuvering performance data for the U.S. Navy's submarine fleet. These models, configured to the specifications of the ship and program, are approximately 20 feet long and 2 feet in diameter, which results in roughly a 1/20th scale model of the full-scale submarine. Fig. 2 shows an AM sitting in a cradle at NSWCCD. The testing group has the capability of having three of these models assembled at any one time and any submarine in any configuration in the Navy's fleet can be replicated and tested. Future submarine designs are also replicated and tested.

Fig. 2. Autonomous Model

The AMs are deployed in indoor or outdoor facilities. While at the surface and down to a depth of about 20 feet an operator station on shore can communicate with the model over a VHF radio link. This communication is used to monitor select data channels, set up run parameters, terminate autonomous operation, and manually operate the AM if desired. Model data files are transferred off of the model when convenient over a wired Ethernet connection. The batteries that power the AM are charged from a charging station while the model is docked in the water or on shore after recovery.

B. Model Mechanical Structure

The AM is divided into three main sections: The center section is an aluminum pressure vessel that contains the majority of the electronics and a portion of the batteries, while the forward and aft sections are flooded with a fiberglass hull and contain smaller pressure vessels, cabling, aluminum ballast tanks, and buoyancy. These three sections can be separated for interchangeability and configurability between models. Additional flooded sections can also be added in-line between the three sections to extend the length. The flooded fiberglass sections have anodized aluminum rings and rails to provide structural stability and mounting points for internal components.

C. Propulsion System

The AM propeller, made of a molded plastic compound or 3D printed in SLA, is driven by a Briggs and Stratton Etek 48V Brushed DC motor through a 1:3 gear ratio. The propeller shaft is equipped with a BEI 5000 pulses per revolution encoder to provide RPM and propeller position feedback. The motor is controlled with a Roboteq HDC 2472S motor controller that uses the encoder RPM as feedback for closed loop control. The propeller drive system is housed in an anodized aluminum submersible housing with a shaft seal through which the approximately 5 foot long shaft passes.

D. Steering and Diving System

The rudder, stern planes, and forward planes are driven by Tonegawa Seiko SSPS submersible servo motors controlled by a Roboteq SDC 2100 brushless motor controller. The plane position for controller feedback is measured with Macro Sensor LVDTs attached to each plane shaft through a cable and pulley system. This system can control plane position to a 0.1 degree accuracy.

E. Navigation System

The AM is equipped with an ixBlue PHINS Inertial Navigation System (INS) which provides a full suite of navigation data to the AM control system, including position, velocities, accelerations, and acceleration rates. The PHINS calculates this information using a Kalman filter sensor fusion algorithm that uses data collected from its internal inertial sensors along with data from the following navigation sensors installed in the AM: An Ashtech ProFlex lite RTK GPS system, a Honeywell Sensotec pressure sensor, and a RDI Workhorse Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP). Two to three additional pressure sensors are also installed in the model to give the AM redundancy checks on pitch and roll. The AM independently collects data from all of these navigation sensors to log with the rest of the maneuvering data. A long baseline (LBL) acoustic positioning system is currently being developed using a Benthos ATM-903 acoustic modem and four Benthos SM-975 smart modem nodes. The AM will calculate position using the acoustic system and send a GPS-like NMEA message to the PHINS to contribute to the fusion algorithm particularly when the AM is submerged and lacking GPS signal.

F. Power System

The AM is powered by six 12 volt lithium phosphate batteries as part of a Valence U-charge XP power system. The batteries are organized in two banks: a four battery bank for the propulsion system (PBAT) and a two battery bank for the rest of the electronics (EBAT). PBAT is located in an anodized aluminum box in the forward section of the AM and EBAT is located in the center pressure vessel with the main electronics. The EBAT power distribution is handled by three voltage regulation boards in the AM, one in the center pressure vessel, and two in individual pressure vessels in the forward and aft sections of the AM. This board uses Syncor InQor voltage filters and regulators to provide clean voltage supplies at +24V, +15V, -15V, +12V, and +5V to components throughout the model. This distributed system allows components to be added to any section of the model and have the requisite voltage supply available. A Valence battery management system (BMS) is used to handle charging and battery safety functions. When fully charged the batteries can last for up to 20 hours of continuous operation. Charging takes about 2 hours at an initial charging current of 55 amps.

G. Maneuvering Load Measurements

AM appendage loads and relative body forces are collected for all relevant components for a particular test to provide a full

understanding of the hydrodynamic maneuvering characteristics. The propulsor is mounted to AMTI 6 DOF dynamometers for load measurement. The control planes are instrumented with 3 or 6 DOF dynamometers that are assembled at NSWCCD using Vishay strain gauges. Other relative body forces, including sail loads, deck loads, or other added appendages can be instrumented with 3 DOF Kistler gauges combined in an assembly to provide 6 DOF load measurements.

H. Data Acquisition and Control System

The data acquisition (DAQ) and control system on the AM is built on a National Instruments (NI) Hardware and LabVIEW software architecture. At the core of this system is an Intel Ivy Bridge low power i5 quad core processor computer running a LabVIEW Real-Time (LVRT) operating system. This computer is equipped with a NI PCIe 6353 DAQ card for collecting and controlling analog and digital signals locally in the center pressure vessel and an EtherCAT compatible Intel PRO/1000 PT network adapter for collecting and controlling signals to and from instruments distributed in the forward and aft sections of the AM through an NI-9144 EtherCAT chassis. These distributed chassis, located in their own pressure housings, can be equipped with up to eight NI C-series modules each for data collection and control. Table 1 lists the C-series modules used for typical data acquisition channels in the AM.

The AM is also equipped with a NI sbRIO-9642, which is an embedded single board computer paired with a FPGA, as a failsafe system. This system monitors and interfaces with critical systems on the AM and performs recovery actions in the event of several critical failure scenarios, including computer failure. An additional computer with an Intel Haswell i5 processor running Windows OS is also installed in the system to provide a platform for other programs to interface with and control the AM. All computer systems are connected via a gigabit Ethernet switch which is also connected to a submersible connector on the center pressure vessel lid for external connection while docked. Lantronix UDS-2100 serial to Ethernet converters are used to communicate with serial instruments in the model. A Raspberry Pi 2 computer is set up as an NTP server for time synchronization on the network using the RTK GPS system as a time standard. The AM sends and receives data packets from a shore computer via a Freewave F50EX008-2 RF 250MHz modem. Fig. 3 shows a diagram of the DAQ and software architecture of the AM.

TABLE I. NI C-SERIES MODULES

NI C-series Module	Signal Description
NI-9237	+/- 25 mV/V Bridge Analog Input with anti-aliasing filter, 50 kS/s
NI-9239	+/- 10V Analog Input with anti-aliasing filter, 50 kS/s
NI-9263	+/- 10V Analog Output, 100 kS/s
NI-9401	5V/TTL Bidirectional Digital I/O

Fig. 3. AM Software and DAQ System Architecture.

I. Software

There are four top level programs that run the AM. Three run on the LVRT computer in the AM electronics pressure vessel and govern the data collection and basic I/O, vehicle control, and data logging. The other runs on the shore operator station and controls user interaction with the AM.

The program that runs the data collection and basic I/O is termed the On Board Computer (OBC). It is a highly configurable program that can communicate with nearly any RS232, Ethernet, or EtherCAT device as well as analog and digital I/O. The OBC program is configured at run time using an INI file with a section for each device and keys to configure the parameters for communicating with that device. Other than the interface details the OBC does not have any knowledge of the devices with which it is communicating, and once it has collected all of the data in a time step, it packages it into a UDP packet for use by the other programs.

The vehicle control and autonomy is performed by a program called the Control Computer (CC). The CC uses the same INI file as the OBC with additional files to further specify the information in any collected Ethernet packets as well as another INI file with calibration information to scale the collected data to engineering units. The CC is additionally responsible for vehicle control and autonomy and has automatic controllers for heading, depth, and RPM. The CC has the ability to run an interpreted scripting language for more complex autonomous behavior. The scripting is capable of reading any data channel decoded by the CC and can issue commands to control surfaces, ballast, and the automatic controllers. It has basic programming language functionality such as conditional logic, looping, variables, and a variety of mathematical operations. The CC's final task is to communicate with the shore

computer, sending status and basic state information and receiving commands over the RF link.

The Data Logger (DL) program is a simple program that reads all of the Ethernet traffic between the OBC, CC and shore, decodes the data, and stores it in a NI TDMS file. The OBC, CC, and DL run on the same computer but can be separated due to the flexibility of using UDP communications.

The Shore Program is the user interface to the AM. It receives status information from the AM and displays it in useful plots and gauges for the operator. The operator can interact with the GUI and drive the AM in manual mode using a handheld controller or dedicated console controller. The shore program can also issue commands to the automatic controllers on the CC or trigger the start of a script to be interpreted on the CC.

III. TESTING FACILITIES

A. Indoor Facility

The Maneuvering and Seakeeping (MASK) Basin (Fig. 4) is a freshwater tank measuring 360 x 240 feet with a depth of 20 feet for 2/3 of the basin with a 30 foot deep trench covering the other third. The MASK is also equipped with a 216 paddle wave maker that can generate model-scale sea states for seakeeping testing. For typical AM test runs in the MASK, the AM is stationed in one corner of the MASK and manually pushed to the required depth for the run. Then autonomous operation is initiated and the AM performs the desired sequence of maneuvers. At the end of the run, the AM surfaces and is then manually driven back to the starting point for another run. The MASK offers several advantages for AM testing, including easy access to labs for spare equipment and repairs, fast deployment and recovery times, and full visibility of the AM throughout test runs. Limitations of testing in the MASK include limited test area and depth for maneuvers, lack of exact navigation positioning, and AM and facility damage concerns with the

Fig. 4. AM Testing in the MASK

Fig. 5. AM Testing at the Outdoor Facility

potential of running the AM into the basin walls. These limitations restrict the amount of autonomous operation that can be utilized.

B. Outdoor Facility

The AM is tested outdoors at a freshwater reservoir (Fig. 5). The facility provides a primary test area of about 2000 x 1000 feet with depth ranging from 10 to 50 feet. The facility is equipped with a ramp and winch for deployment and recovery of the AM and various office and lab trailers for operations support. The reservoir additionally offers the ability to provide RTK GPS and acoustic LBL positioning of the AM. Currently, the operations at this facility are much the same as the MASK except the larger range and depth provide more flexibility in the maneuvers that can be performed. In the future as the advanced navigation features of the AM are refined and the control system is updated, the AM will be able to perform consecutive test runs autonomously at the reservoir. The AM will dive to depth and perform maneuvers back to back, occasionally surfacing to obtain refined positioning, all without any interaction from the at-shore user.

IV. EXAMPLE TEST RESULTS

In this section select channels are presented from two example test runs performed by the AM. The data presented here is an example of the type of data analysis that can be performed using the AM maneuvering runs. More specifically, these are examples of how the navigation and load measurement data can be used to determine the hydrodynamic maneuvering characteristics of underwater vehicles. AM data are also used for validation of simulation and computational calculations to help refine hydrodynamic models.

The first example run is a controlled turn. In this run the model is programmed to achieve a steady heading, depth, and pitch at a constant RPM for the turn approach. Once the steady approach is achieved, the model moves the rudder to a fixed port turn position at a pre-programmed rate and holds the rudder position for the remainder of the run while the controller

Fig. 6. Controlled Turn Data

continues to hold depth and RPM. Fig. 6 shows the data collected for rudder position, rudder transverse loading, and roll for the run. During the first section of the run, the rudder position can be observed to be moving as the controller is attempting to achieve a steady heading. Once the approach is steady and the rudder is moved to a fixed turn angle, the rudder load can be seen to increase, and then decrease as the AM begins to steady in the turn. In the analysis of the roll data, the AM initially rolls outward slightly when the rudder is thrown and the force on the rudder pushes the top of the model outward, then it rolls back inward as an angle of attack is achieved on the AM sail and the sail lift force pushes the top of the model into the turn.

The second example test run is a deceleration run. In this run the AM achieves a steady approach as in the controlled turn, but then follows a pre-programmed deceleration curve with propeller RPM control, while holding plane angles steady until the model eventually comes to a stop. Fig. 7 shows the RPM,

Fig. 7. Deceleration Data

propeller torque, and AM heading during the run. As the RPM decreases the propeller torque changes direction until finally the model comes to a stop and the RPM is set to zero. More interestingly, the heading data shows that the model swerves quickly in the starboard direction and then back to port as the RPM goes through the deceleration curve.

V. SUMMARY

The AM developed by the Hydrodynamics Testing Branch at NSWCCD is a unique system for testing hydrodynamic maneuvering characteristics of underwater vehicles. Combining autonomous vehicle technology with a sophisticated data acquisition system, the system is capable of performing complex maneuvers while collecting high fidelity data to facilitate understanding the hydrodynamic system. In addition to being used as a maneuvering testing platform, the AM has also been used as an AUV in conjunction with autonomous surface vehicles (ASV) to develop control algorithms for autonomous multi-vehicle tracking and avoidance behavior [2]. Furthermore, the Hydrodynamics Testing Branch has the capability to develop, instrument, and test additional platforms for maneuvering testing, for both model-scale testing of large vehicles and full-scale testing of smaller vehicles.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors of this paper would like to thank all the members of the Hydrodynamics Testing Branch at NSWCCD for their roles in the development and testing of the Autonomous Models.

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